

Generation of observation equation coefficients

The programs SCANG and SCANS can be used to generate the set of observation equation coefficients (in ecliptical coordinates)

$$P_1 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \lambda \cos \beta}, \quad P_2 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \beta}, \quad P_3 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \mu_\lambda \cos \beta}, \quad P_4 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \mu_\beta}, \quad P_5 = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \Pi}$$

The program listings are mostly self-explanatory; only a few comments.

1. Program SCANG produces a file with one record per spin about $\underline{z}$, containing time (in days from JD2446800) and rectangular ecliptical coordinates of the sun (in AU) and $\underline{z}$ (unit vector). For a test run, suitable input values are the default values:

TBEG = 0. TEND = 913. REVPD = 1. VAR = 1.
 ANY0 = 0. XI = .666 AK = 6.8

Part of the resulting spin table is shown in listing 2a (produced by SCANT). For a realistic run, the input values could be:

TBEG = 0. TEND = 913. REVPD = 12. VAR = 1.
 ANY0 = 0. XI = .7505 AK = 6.4

2. Program SCANT prints a nice table of the spins generated by SCANG. See printout for the test case above (2a).

3. Program SCANS finds the scans across a given point (λ, β) and computes the various angles etc. For each scan, the following data is printed (and written on a new file):

NR, T, SINZ = observation number, time (days), $\sin \zeta$
 PSI = ψ = position angle of scan (see figure below)
 CAL = $\partial \eta / (\partial \lambda \cos \beta)$, CB = $\partial \eta / \partial \beta$, CP = $\partial \eta / \partial \Pi$

The remaining two derivatives (p_3 and p_4) for the proper motions are:

$$p_3 = \frac{T - \text{TEPOCH}}{365.25} P_1, \quad p_4 = \frac{T - \text{TEPOCH}}{365.25} P_2$$

where e.g. TEPOCH = (TBEG + TEND)/2.

Input: FOVW = .0157 rad (= 0.9°), AL, B = long. and lat. of star.

For a test run, use AL = 0. and B = 1. together with the spin table 2a; this should produce the observations in listing 3c with integer T (since REVPD = 10. was actually used for this listing). Listings 3a,b,d are for other latitudes.

$\underline{z}$ = z axis

$\underline{u}$ = direction to star

$\underline{s}$ = direction to sun x distance (AU)

FORMULAE

Revolving Scanning Law (SCANG)

The spin axis $\underline{z} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\beta_2 \cos\lambda_2 \\ \cos\beta_2 \sin\lambda_2 \\ \sin\beta_2 \end{pmatrix}$ is defined relative to the sun

[at (λ_1, β_1)] by the two angles $\xi =$ revolving angle (43°) and $\nu =$ revolving phase. The latter is obtained by integrating

$$\frac{d\nu}{d\lambda_1} = \frac{1}{\sin\xi} \left\{ \sin\nu \cos\xi + \sqrt{\alpha^2 - \left(\frac{d\xi}{d\lambda_1} + \cos\nu\right)^2} \right\}$$

where $\alpha \equiv |\dot{\underline{z}}|/\dot{\lambda}_1$ is a constant. This gives approximately K revolutions per year if $\alpha^2 = 1.5 + (K^2 - 1) \sin^2\xi$.

The pole (λ_2, β_2) is then obtained from

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sin\beta_2 &= \sin\xi \sin\nu \\ \tan(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1) &= \tan\xi \cos\nu \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Solar coordinates $\underline{s} = R_0 \begin{pmatrix} \cos\beta_s \cos\lambda_s \\ \cos\beta_s \sin\lambda_s \\ \sin\beta_s \end{pmatrix}$ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \beta_s = 0 \\ \lambda_s = \text{function of } t \\ R_0 = \text{function of time [AU]} \end{array} \right.$

Observation Geometry (SCANS)

The condition that a star at (λ, β) is observed in a given spin is

$$|\xi| < \frac{1}{2} \text{FOVW} = 0.45. \quad \text{Here } \sin\xi = \underline{u} \cdot \underline{z} \quad \text{with } \underline{u} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\beta \cos\lambda \\ \cos\beta \sin\lambda \\ \sin\beta \end{pmatrix}$$

The "position angle" of scan, ψ , is obtained from

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \cos\psi &= \cos\beta_2 \sin(\lambda - \lambda_2) / \cos\xi \\ \sin\psi &= (\sin\beta_2 - \sin\beta \sin\xi) / (\cos\xi \cos\beta) \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \psi$$

Then

$$\frac{\partial\eta}{\partial\lambda \cos\beta} = \sin\psi / \cos\xi \quad \frac{\partial\eta}{\partial\beta} = \cos\psi / \cos\xi$$

and

$$\frac{\partial\eta}{\partial T} = \underline{s} \cdot (\underline{z} \wedge \underline{u}) / \cos^2\xi$$